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The Doctrine of Public Trust: Its Judicial Invocation in Bangladesh and the Future Potentials

Azhar U. Bhuiyan*

Abstract: The Doctrine of Public Trust (DPT), despite its south Asian root and constitutional base, was introduced late into the constitutional law of Bangladesh. In 2010, the Supreme Court of Bangladesh felt it was time for them to adopt DPT, and thus without offering any methodological justification as to how they are bringing a US doctrine in our constitutional jurisprudence, the Court applied the DPT in a matter involving protection of a natural resource-gas. However, while the DPT could play its role in the protection of public properties in Bangladesh in only a limited number of cases, that too after 2010, it does have the potential to play bigger role in Bangladesh given its growth in other parts of the world. This article traces the development of this doctrine in Bangladesh and its application. At the same time, it responds to the existing critiques of the DPT that are raised against its judicial invocation in the west from the perspective of Bangladesh. Lastly, this article will project the future path of the DPT in Bangladesh. This article adds significantly to the existing body of legal literature by theorising a test with the existing judicial developments of the doctrine in Bangladesh.

Keywords: Constitution of Bangladesh, doctrine of public trust, and public property.

1. Introduction

Despite being an evolving issue, the Doctrine of Public Trust (DPT) has not received any scholarly attention in Bangladesh. Even, the Supreme Court of Bangladesh (SCB) has raised this concern in one of its recent observations.¹

The Doctrine of Public Trust (DPT) has prominently developed as an enforceable legal doctrine in the 20th century United States (US) with the seminal article authored by Professor Joseph Sax.² Sax grounded the basis of the doctrine in ancient Roman law and common law. In the south Asian subcontinent, the Indian Judiciary was the first to incorporate the entire domain of US development of the DPT through *MC Mehta v Kamal Nath*.³ All these developments based on the ancient Roman concept of *res communis* has been questionable by US academics on the ground that Roman Law did not have any

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¹ *Human Rights & Peace for Bangladesh v Bangladesh* (2019) WP No 13989/2016 at 257.

² See for details, Joseph L. Sax, 'The Public Trust Doctrine in Natural Resource Law: Effective Judicial Intervention' (1970) 68 Michigan Law Review 471.

³ *M C Mehta v Kamal Nath & Ors* (1997) 1 SCC 388.

concept of preserving public trust properties and Magna Carta had nothing to do with the community rights of the citizens.⁴ While relying much on the western notion of the DPT, the south Asian courts have ignored, what the International Court of Justice did not, the south Asian autochthonous origin of the doctrine. This article attempts to point out the south Asian autochthonous origin of the doctrine and traces its historical trajectory in Bangladesh.

At first this paper investigates the historical evolution of the DPT as it was developed. It starts by focusing on the widely accepted belief that the DPT has its origin in ancient Roman law and later on was borrowed by the English Common Law through the incorporation of the doctrine in the Magna Carta. The paper addresses the concerns raised by Professor Huffman and shows that even if his claim is true, the DPT has its autochthonous south Asian root. Therefore, the shaky history in the west cannot overrule the development of the DPT in this part of the world. In the next part, the paper analyses the current status of the DPT in Bangladesh in view of all four cases - *Shah Abdul Hannan*,⁵ *Faridul Alam*,⁶ *HRPB (2010)*,⁷ *HRPB (2019)*,⁸ decided by the SCB. It also discusses the role of the legislature apart from the court in fulfilling the obligation stemming from the DPT as incorporated in the Constitution of Bangladesh. It analyses the fiduciary duties of the trustees of the public trust properties in light of the latest judicial development in Bangladesh.

Later, this paper points out the criticism of the DPT in the context of Bangladesh and addresses such criticisms. It points out three popularly raised criticisms: shaky legal background, apparent inconsistency with the concept of rule of law and finally the issue of separation of powers. In the next part, this paper emphasises on the role of the legal community in not creating any bar in the development of the DPT. This paper asserts that the DPT is an important legal fiction acknowledged and utilized by the SCB. At the same time, it theorizes a cost-benefit analysis test taking into consideration the overall development of the doctrine in Bangladesh. This paper ends by projecting the future use of the DPT in Bangladesh.

⁴ See for details, James L Huffman, 'Speaking Inconvenient Truths: A History of Public Trust Doctrine' (2007) 18 *Duke Environmental Law and Policy Forum* 1 (argues that the origin of DPT is not based on true facts to the extent of preserving public rights).

⁵ *Shah Abdul Hannan v Bangladesh* (2011) 16 BLC 386.

⁶ *Faridul Alam v Bangladesh* (2010) 18 BLT 323.

⁷ *Human Rights & Peace for Bangladesh v Bangladesh* (2010) 22 BLC 48.

⁸ *Human Rights & Peace for Bangladesh v Bangladesh* (2019) WP No 13989/2016.

2. The historical trajectory of the public trust doctrine

2.1. A transplantation from ancient roman law or one of south Asian autochthonous origin?

A big majority of the legal scholars from the west trace the origin of the DPT in the concept of 'common properties' (*res communis*)⁹ as found in the ancient Justinian Code of 530 A.D where it was stated: "by the law of nature, these things are common to mankind – the air, running water, the sea, and consequently the shores of the sea..."¹⁰ On the contrary, it has been argued that relying on this provision of Justinian Code to locate the origin of 'public trust' was a 'creative judicial misunderstanding' of the Roman Law.¹¹ The reason behind such an argument is the qualifiers after the above quotation from Justinian Code, "whilst he abstains from damaging farms, monuments, edifices, etc. which are not in common as the sea is", have been always ignored except the minority opinion in the *Glass v Goeckel*.¹² Moreover, in the Roman Empire, sea shores or submerged lands were often privately owned and were free to be taken.¹³ Therefore, it seems that there is a debate as to the origin of the DPT in Roman law. The High Court Division (HCD) of the SCB has also endorsed the trend in the U.S. academia and maintained that the current conception on the 'environment' bears a close resemblance to the roman origin of DPT.¹⁴ While adopting such a position, this south Asian court seems to ignore the South Asian origin of the doctrine in Sri Lanka.

⁹ See for details, Joseph L. Sax, 'Liberating the Public Trust Doctrine from its Historical Shackles' (1980) 14(2) University of California Davis Law Review 185.

¹⁰ See for example, Robert Haskell Abrams, 'Governmental Expansion of Recreational Water Use Opportunities' (1980) 59(2&3) Oregon Law Review 159, 162; Seldon, 'Wherever the Water Flows: Lyon Applies the Public Trust to Non-Tidal Water' (1983) 11 Ecology Law Quarterly 21, 26. However, there is an interesting argument on the origin of the doctrine in Sri Lanka. See for details, Rajitha Perera, 'The Public Trust Doctrine' (2016) 4 Judicial Service Association of Sri Lanka Law Journal <https://www.academia.edu/37942953/The_Public_Trust_Doctrine> accessed 16 April 2020. On the other hand, tracing the origin of the public trust doctrine has been considered as another 'creative judicial misunderstanding' of the Roman Law. See for details, Carl Shadi Paganelli, 'Creative Judicial Misunderstanding: Misapplication of the Public Trust Doctrine in Michigan' (2007) 58 Hastings Law Journal 1095, 1096.

¹¹ See for details, Carl Shadi Paganelli, 'Creative Judicial Misunderstanding: Misapplication of the Public Trust Doctrine in Michigan' (2007) 58 Hastings Law Journal 1095, 1096; also see James L. Huffman, 'Protecting the Great Lakes: The Allure and Limitations of the Public Trust Doctrine' (2016) 93 University of Detroit Mercy Law Review 239.

¹² *Glass v Goeckel* (2005) 703 N.W.2d 58.

¹³ See for details, Patrick Deveney, 'Title, Jus Publicum, and the Public Trust: An Historical Analysis' (1976) 1 Sea Grant Law Journal 13, 30.

¹⁴ See for details, *Faridul Alam v Bangladesh* (2010) 30 BLD 500; *Human Rights & Peace for Bangladesh v Bangladesh* (2019) Writ Petition No 13989/2016 <http://www.supremecourt.gov.bd/resources/documents/1048627_W.P.13989of2016.pdf> accessed 17 April 2020.

The concept of guardianship over public properties in south Asia, specifically in Sri Lanka dates back to the third century BC.¹⁵ According to the historical accounts¹⁶, in 223 BC, the King of this region Devanampiya Tissa went for an animal hunting. Emperor Asoka's¹⁷ son Arahat Mahinda preached to him the following sermon:

O great King, the birds of the air and the beasts have as equal a right to live and move about in any part of the land as thou. The land belongs to the people and all living beings; thou art only the guardian of it...¹⁸

Although the Justinian Code and the Mahāvamsa¹⁹ (the Great Chronicle of Ceylon) conceptually overlaps in providing protection to the elements of environment, public property, a critical look into these two sources shows that the latter imports deeper and advanced version of environmental philosophy. Justinian recognized the air, running water, the sea, and consequently the shores of the sea, as 'common property' or in other words property enjoyable by all. On the contrary, the Mahāvamsa's thoughts go deep down to the preservation of such elements of nature and the role of the king (or ruler, i.e. government) as the guardian of such public properties. The most significant part of the Sri Lankan origin is that the king or the ruler was placed in the position of guardian which we can directly relate to the modern concept of 'public trust'.²⁰ Therefore, there remains no doubt as to the south Asian origin of the doctrine.

2.2. European civil and common law antecedents

Although there is debate as to the origin of the doctrine in Rome or in South Asia, there is no question on the fact that it is the English Law that finally gave legal shape to the DPT to restrict the proprietary control of the King over certain natural resources. The pedigree of the doctrine can be found in Chapters 16²¹ and 23²² of the Magna Carta although it is correct to say that these chapters have a very thin link to the modern understanding of the doctrine. At the same time, it

¹⁵ *Hungary v Slovakia* (Gabčíkovo-Nagymaros Project) [1997] ICJ Rep 7.

¹⁶ Such an account has been cited even in the judgment of the International Court of Justice in the Gabčíkovo-Nagymaros Project Case.

¹⁷ Ashok, also known as Ashoka the Great, was an Indian emperor of the Maurya Dynasty, who ruled almost all of the Indian subcontinent from c. 268 to 232 BC.

¹⁸ See for details, Walpola Rāhula, *History of Buddhism in Ceylon: the Anuradhapura period, 3d century BC-10th century AC*. (M.D. Gunasena, 1956) 217-221.

¹⁹ See generally, Wilhelm Geiger and Mabel Haynes Bode, *The Mahāvamsa, Or, The Great Chronicle of Ceylon by Mahanama* (Asian Educational Services, 1993).

²⁰ See for details, Rajitha Perera (n 10) 1-4.

²¹ Chapter 16 of Magna Carta states: "No riverbanks shall be placed in defense from henceforth except such as were so placed in the time of King Henry, our grandfather, by the same places and the same bounds as they were to be in his time."

²² Chapter 23 of Magna Carta provides that: "All weirs for the future shall be utterly put down on the Thames and Medway and throughout all England, except on the seashore."

must be admitted that the concept of public trust doctrine was finally given a legal shape by the European civil and common law antecedents. Spain recognized a public right to navigable waterways in the thirteenth century.²³ The French Civil Code maintained that navigable rivers and streams, beaches, ports and harbors shall be treated as common property.²⁴ Incorporation of this doctrine into the legal texts to impose obligation on the government or the ruler to protect the properties, however, was oblivious to grant public rights that could be legally enforceable against a recalcitrant government for a long time.²⁵

2.3. Trajectory of DPT in Bangladesh through India: inspiration from the United States

For a long time, almost the entire sub-continent was ruled by the British colonizers. Inspirations from Magna Carta and other common law precepts, however, did not reach the subcontinent. Understandably, the intention of the colonizers was to exploit the resources of the sub-continent to enrich themselves.²⁶ There was no intention in the British colonizers to preserve and protect any resources of the sub-continent. That is perhaps the most plausible reason why the countries in south Asian sub-continent had to wait till 1997 to recognize the 'DPT' formally within their laws of the lands.²⁷

In the south Asian sub-continent, India is the first country to recognize DPT as a law of the land. In *M C Mehta v Kamal Nath*²⁸, the petitioner built a motel at the delta of a river while it changed the course of the river. The Ministry of Environment was responsible for overlooking such activities. Notably, the DPT did not specifically exist in the constitutional law of India then. The change of course of the river caused flooding in the nearby villages. To adjudicate the case, the Indian Supreme Court relied on the reasoning offered by the celebrated work of the U.S. Academic Joseph Sax²⁹ where he argued that the public must have an enforceable right against the government to protect the natural resources of the country from commercial exploitation. The Court located the origin of the DPT in the common law and ended up adopting the entirety of the American version

²³ See for details, Samuel Parsons Scott (ed) Robert I. Burns, *Las Siete partidas, Vol IV (in English Family, Commerce, and the Sea: The Worlds of Women and Merchants)* (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 2001) ("Rivers, harbors, and public highways belong to all persons in common . . .").

²⁴ French Civil Code, Article 538.

²⁵ *M C Mehta v Kamal Nath & Ors* (1997) 1 SCC 388.

²⁶ For an account of the approach of the British colonizers in ruling the Indian sub-continent, see Shoshi Tharoor, *An Era of Darkness: The British Empire in India* (Aleph Book Company 2011).

²⁷ *M C Mehta* (n 25).

²⁸ *ibid.*

²⁹ See for details, Joseph L. Sax, 'The Public Trust Doctrine in Natural Resource Law: Effective Judicial Intervention' (1970) 68 Michigan Law Review 471.

DPT in a wholesale basis.³⁰ Within the next three years, the Supreme Court of India could find the constitutional abode of the DPT in Article 21 by widening the ambit of the right to life.³¹ However, till date there exists no legislation in India to regulate the scope of the DPT.

The journey of DPT in Bangladesh started from the very beginning of its independence. Two reasons can be attributed behind this. Firstly, Bangladesh has also been a part of the British colony and the legal system is deeply influenced by the common law traditions. Secondly, it has been often argued by the historians that one environmental disaster prior to 1971 made the destined break-up of Pakistan speedy.³² Therefore, the political leadership of independent Bangladesh was really aware of the environmental needs of the country and thus incorporated the DPT in Article 21 of the Constitution. However, SCB took long time to flesh out the DPT as such from the language of Article 21. As a result, there has been only 4 cases so far where the SCB utilized the concept of DPT. As summarised in the following table, they also seem to have followed the Indian line of reasoning:

Name of the Case	Judge	Reasoning	Relied on	Subject matter
<i>Shah Abdul Hannan v Bangladesh</i> ³³ (2010)	A.H.M. Shamsuddin Choudhury	a) DPT is part of English Common Law b) Time has come to adopt the theory Indian judiciary adopted	MC Mehta v Kamal Nath ³⁴	Natural Resources: Gas
<i>Faridul Alam v Bangladesh</i> ³⁵ (2010)	Md. Mamtaz Uddin Ahmed	DPT is part of English Common Law	a) MC Mehta v Kamal Nath ³⁶ b) Joseph Sax's Article	Lease for hotel/motel in the Coxs' Bazar Sea beach area
<i>Human Rights & Peace for Bangladesh v Bangladesh</i> ³⁷ (2010)	Md. Rezaul Hasan	The Indian adoption of DPT is of great persuasive value.	M C Mehta v Kamal Nath ³⁸	Preservation and protection of 'Karnaphuli' river

³⁰ *M C Mehta* (n 25) para 269, 270.

³¹ *M.I. Builders Private Ltd. v Radhey Shyam Sahu* (1999) 6 SCC 464, 466.

³² See for details, Naomi Hossain, 'The 1970 Bhola cyclone, nationalist politics, and the subsistence crisis contract in Bangladesh' (2018) 42(1) *Disasters* 187-203.

³³ *Shah Abdul Hannan v Bangladesh* (2011) 16 BLC 386.

³⁴ *M C Mehta* (n 25).

³⁵ *Faridul Alam v Bangladesh* (2010) 18 BLT 323.

³⁶ *M C Mehta* (n 25).

³⁷ *Human Rights & Peace for Bangladesh v Bangladesh* (2010) 22 BLC 48.

³⁸ *M C Mehta* (n 25).

Name of the Case	Judge	Reasoning	Relied on	Subject matter
<i>Human Rights & Peace for Bangladesh v Bangladesh</i> ³⁹ (2019)	Md. Ashraful Kamal	a) Article 21 (duties of citizens and of public servants) b) Article 18A (protection and improvement of environment and biodiversity) c) Article 31 (right to protection of law) and 32 (protection of right to life and personal liberty)	a) MC Mehta v Kamal Nath b) Joseph Sax's Article	Preservation and protection of 'Turag' river

Figure 1: Cases involving DPT in Bangladesh

If we critically delve into the root of the DPT in Bangladesh, it is evident that the judiciary was, at first, not certain about the constitutional position of the doctrine in Bangladesh. Rather the judiciary kept taking a functionalist approach to the doctrine relying on the English Common Law precepts and persuasive authority of the Indian cases. In the first two cases, the judges as well as the lawyers, refrained from referring to any constitutional provision in Bangladesh. This raises an important question as to the methodology of transplantation of constitutional doctrines. However, in the third case, the Judiciary could reach a more transparent position. In this case, the Court was of the view that although Article 18A was later entrenched into the constitution through an amendment after 39 years of its establishment and the right to life was yet show its elasticity, the constituent assembly led by father of the nation Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman incorporated the concept of public trust in the Part II (Fundamental Principles of State Policy (FPSP)) of the 1972 Constitution making the it the first constitution ever to recognize DPT. Article 21(1) of the Bangladesh Constitution states that:

It is the duty of every citizen to observe the Constitution and the laws to maintain discipline, to perform public duties and *to protect public property.*
(emphasis on the italic portion)

Although following the classical position of the FPSPs, it can be argued that provisions of the part II are not judicially enforceable, it is submitted that considering the modern developments in several case laws⁴⁰ and academic commentaries⁴¹, the Part II provision of the Constitution is definitely negatively

³⁹ *Human Rights & Peace for Bangladesh v Bangladesh* (2019) WP No 13989/2016.

⁴⁰ See for details, *Chairman, National Board of Revenue v Advocate Julhas Uddin* (2010) 15 MLR (AD) 457; *Major General K M Shafiullah v Bangladesh* (2009) Writ Petition no. 4313/2009.

⁴¹ See for details, Muhammad Ekramul Haque, 'Legal and Constitutional Status of the Fundamental Principles of State Policy as Embodied in the Constitution of Bangladesh' (2005) 16(1) Journal of the Faculty of Law 45-81; Muhammad Ekramul Haque, 'The Bangladesh Constitutional Framework and Human Rights' (2011) 22 (1) Dhaka University Law Journal 55-79; Muhammad

enforceable if not positively. On the other hand, even before these judicial pronouncements and academic commentaries, there was no doubt as to the constitutional obligation on the state to consider the provisions of Part II in the governance of Bangladesh, to apply them while making laws, to use them as a guide to interpretation of the constitution and of other laws, to use them as the basis of the work of the state and of its citizens.⁴² Therefore, a close reading of these case law, academic commentaries and the clear constitutional provision in Article 8(2) read with Article 21(1) provides that there is at least a negative obligation on the state to protect public property. The concept of DPT develops on the concept of public property.⁴³ In addition after the entrenchment of the Article 18A in the Bangladesh Constitution, and expansion of the meaning of right to life under Article 32 of the Constitution, there remains no doubt as to the constitutional abode of the DPT in Bangladesh. This is how so far the DPT has developed in Bangladesh.

3. The public trust doctrine in Bangladesh: analyzing the present

3.1. Meaning and scope

Constitutional Law jurist in Bangladesh Mahmudul Islam relied on the definition of the Black's Law Dictionary to define the DPT. It defines as follows:

The doctrine provides that submerged and submersible lands are preserved for public use in navigation, fishing and recreation and State as a trustee for the people, bears the responsibility of preserving and protecting the right of the public to the use of the waters for those purposes.⁴⁴

The opinion of Mahmudul Islam in the context on 2020 seems a bit backdated because around the globe DPT has evolved beyond the traditional concept of navigation, fishing and recreation rights. However, Mahmudul Islam actively referred to the approach of the Indian Supreme Court in the *MC Mehta v Kamal Nath* on which the SCB relied on in the *Faridul Alam*. Bangladeshi courts as well the jurists are highly persuaded by the *MC Mehta* dictum where the court "quashed a lease of forest land by the side of a river for interfering with natural flow of the river and ordered the lessee to pay compensation by way of restitution of the environment and ecology."⁴⁵ Bangladesh court, however, expanded the meaning and scope of the doctrine in three subsequent cases.

Ekramul Haque, 'Does Part II of the Constitution of Bangladesh contain only economic and social rights?' (2012) 23(1) Dhaka University Law Journal 45-51.

⁴² Constitution of Bangladesh, art 8(2).

⁴³ *Human Rights & Peace for Bangladesh* (n 39) 157.

⁴⁴ Henry Campbell Black, *Black's Law Dictionary* (6th edn, West Publishing Company 1996) cited in Mahmudul Islam, *Constitutional Law of Bangladesh* (3rd edn, Mullick Brothers Ltd 2012) 258.

⁴⁵ See for details, Mahmudul Islam (n 44) 258.

In *Shah Abdul Hannan*, the petitioners sued “with honest and sincere desire”⁴⁶ to protect natural resources, e.g., gas and coal. Though the case was finally disposed of on a different issue, it was all agreed by both the parties and Shamsuddin Chowdhury J. that DPT is part of English common law and thus it is part of the law of the land. Accordingly, the ‘natural and mineral resources’ like natural gas is entitled to the protection of public trust. The Court transplanted the Indian doctrine of public trust and said that the state’s duty is essentially akin to that of a Trustee of a Public trust, a fiduciary duty to act as protectors. By doing so, the Court expanded the scope of the DPT giving protection of public trust to the natural resources. In the second one, *Faridul Alam*, the court did not need to go beyond the traditional meaning of the DPT. Here the DPT was used to direct the government to take steps to protect the ecologically critical area of Cox’s Bazar sea beach. In the third one, *Turag River*, the court utilized the DPT to declare the encroachment of the occupier unlawful and unconstitutional. In this judgment, Ashraful Kamal J. declared all the rivers in Bangladesh a legal person relying on the DPT. Thus, so far, the scope of DPT in Bangladesh has extended to natural resources like gas and coal, sea beach, and rivers. However, the HCD of the SCB has expressly said that new elements shall be added in future in the scope of the DPT.⁴⁷ Therefore, at the moment, it is not possible to provide a conclusive definition or comprehensive scope of the DPT in Bangladesh. Whatever, the definition will turn out to be in future, according to the DPT, the Constitution did not grant the state ownership of forest, wild animals, sea, sea-beach, rivers, and canals. Rather the state is merely in the position of a trustee whose obligation is to protect and develop the public trust properties.

The leading authority on the DPT, Professor Sax found three types of restriction on the authority of the government in dealing with public trust property.⁴⁸ Firstly, the public trust property must be held accessible for use by the general public. Second, the public trust property is invaluable, i.e. the government cannot transfer the property for any amount of compensation. Thirdly, the governmental conduct for relocating the public trust property or subjecting it to uses for the interest of the private persons shall be sceptically looked into by the Judiciary. As the study of cases above shows, the Judiciary of Bangladesh has typically maintained a similar position on the DPT with regard to the restrictions on the governmental authority.

⁴⁶ Hannan (n 33) para 4.

⁴⁷ *Human Rights & Peace for Bangladesh* (n 39) 81.

⁴⁸ See for details, Joseph L. Sax, ‘The Public Trust Doctrine in Natural Resource Law: Effective Judicial Intervention’ (1970) 68 (3) Michigan Law Review 471.

3.2. Application of the doctrine

While the Bangladesh Supreme Court's recognition, reasoning and expansion of the DPT is a welcome development, in general there remains critical questions to be answered in relation to its application in Bangladesh. In the following the role of the courts and the legislature with regard to the DPT shall be discussed with particular focus on the substantive elements of the doctrine.

3.2.1. Role of the courts

Judicial Review of the Administration of the Trust: The HCD of the SCB is constitutionally empowered with the authority of judicial review and thus it can inquire into and provide remedy by "directing a person performing any functions in connection with the affairs of the Republic or of a local authority, to refrain from doing that which he is not permitted by law to do or to do that which he is required by law to do".⁴⁹ From the above discussions, the obligation upon the state towards public trust property is clear. In this circumstance, the courts can make sure that the public trust property is not being used for any purpose other than public's benefit under the constitutional authority of the court. The court can also adjudicate the issue: whether the state has fulfilled its obligation to maintain the public trust. Moreover, the court is the final authority to decide if any particular legislation has questionable content in itself which can be deemed unconstitutional because of being contrary to the DPT.

In all four cases involving DPT in Bangladesh, the suit was filed by public spirited individuals or organizations and the courts readily granted them locus standi.⁵⁰ When a Public Interest Litigation is filed on issues relating to the affairs of the public trust property, the court is obliged to grant locus standi and 'strictly scrutinize'⁵¹ the legality of the affairs of the trust property. Thus, if any legislative action or executive action is contrary to the preservation of public trust property, the courts must step in by inquiring if there is any compelling government interest and if there is no other alternative to do that. However,

⁴⁹ Constitution of Bangladesh, Article 102(2) (a).

⁵⁰ Over the past two decades, the concept of locus standi has been liberalized to a wide extent only to face the abuse of the liberal interpretation and thereafter the courts had to narrow down the scope of the widened locus standi. With the judgment on *NBR v Abu Sayeed* (2013) 18 BLC (AD) 116, the position of the law came to a settled position. See for details, Md Rizwanul Islam and Md Tayeb-Ul-Islam Showrov, 'Sifting through the Maze of 'Person Aggrieved' in Constitutional Public Interest Litigation: Has Abu Saeed Case Ushered a New Dawn?' (2017) 28 Dhaka University Law Journal (Dhaka University Studies Part-F) 155-168.

⁵¹ Although there is no study on the implication of 'doctrine of strict scrutiny' in Bangladesh, the equality clauses of the Constitution of India and Bangladesh are similar. Moreover, the Bangladeshi courts routinely rely on the Indian constitutional jurisprudence unless the constitutional texts are different. For implications of the doctrine of strict scrutiny in India, see Moiz Tundawala, 'Invocation of strict scrutiny in India: Why the Opposition?' (2010) 3 NUJS Law Review 465.

while doing so it is important for the judges to be cautious if they are transgressing the limits of the Constitution itself.

Role of the Legislature: Under the DPT, it is the 'state' that is in charge of the public trust property. It purports to mean that all three branches of the state shall play its expected role to preserve and protect the properties. As the law-making branch of the state, the legislature or the Parliament of Bangladesh has to play its role by enacting laws respecting public trust property. The legislature is the principal trustee of the public trust properties. The Constitutional basis of the DPT is an indication that if any legislative action fails to meet the fiduciary standard of care for the trustees, such actions and standards can be strike down. Moreover, it is also the obligation of the legislature to promote the DPT by enacting legislation for different sectors. Fortunately, the Parliament of Bangladesh has tried to incorporate the concept of DPT into different legislation from the very beginning. Justice Ashrafal Kamal in the *Turag river*⁵² has identified all the legislation that incorporated the concept of DPT, enacted so far:

- a) 'The Bangladesh Wild Life (Preservation) Order, 1973
- b) The Bangladesh Petroleum Act, 1974
- c) The Environment Conservation Act, 1995
- d) The Environment Conservation Rules, 1997
- e) The Environment Court Act, 2000
- f) The Play-ground, Open space, Park and Natural Wetland Conservation Act, 2000
- g) The Climate Change Trust Act, 2010
- h) The Wildlife (Preservation and Security) Act, 2012
- i) The National River Protection Commission Act, 2013
- j) The Bangladesh Water Act, 2013
- k) The Bangladesh Bio-diversity Act, 2017

3.2.2. Fiduciary duties of the trustees

3.2.2.1. Substantive duties

The duty of the public servant: Since the public servants are appointed by the people of this country with the support of the Government, the government officials are legally obliged to maintain the public trust properties.⁵³ If there is any inconsistency in fulfilling the obligation, they are accountable to the people. The people can ensure such accountability through the Government or the Judiciary.

⁵² *Human Rights & Peace for Bangladesh* (n 39).

⁵³ *ibid*, 260.

The duty of the National River Protection Commission: The National River Protection Commission has been declared as the legal guardian (person in loco parentis) of all the rivers of Bangladesh.⁵⁴The Court also imposed obligation on them to protect and develop the rivers and recover those which were encroached unlawfully. Moreover, the organizations of the Government are also made responsible to assist the National River Protection Commission fulfil their responsibilities.⁵⁵

The duty of Bangladesh Bank: The Court imposed an obligation on the central bank of Bangladesh, Bangladesh Bank, to direct all the banks of Bangladesh by a circular to take necessary measures so that no amount of loan is granted against any individual or company who is alleged to be an encroacher of public trust property.⁵⁶ However, mere allegation cannot be considered as a conclusive proof of an offence. Thus, the Banks may be instructed to postpone the entire process of granting loan when the decision makers of the Bank have knowledge about the illegal encroachment of the loan applicant. If after the due process, the loan applicant is acquitted of the charges, the Bank can definitely resume the loan application.

The duty of the National Election Commission: The Court has directed the National Election Commission to include the unlawful encroachment and destroyer of public trust property in the list of conditions for ineligibility in elections in all levels including union, sub-district, district and Parliament.⁵⁷

The duty of protection: The duty of protection to the public trust properties requires an active role on the part of the state. Therefore, the state, i.e. the executive Government and the legislature must take an active role or affirmative actions to preserve and protect the public trust properties. If any backsliding in their role is noticed, the beneficiaries of the public trust properties can sue the state in the court of law for proper remedies. Thus, if any permit of any developmental project involving the public trust property is granted, as the trustee, the state must take an active interest over the project, continue supervision over such project and put an end to such project when it becomes harmful for public interest.

The duty against waste: The Constitution of Bangladesh provides protection for environment not only for the present generation but also for the future generation, thereby including inter-generational equity principle in itself.⁵⁸Indian Supreme Court is of the view that the DPT looks beyond the need of the present

⁵⁴ ibid, 278.

⁵⁵ ibid.

⁵⁶ ibid, 281.

⁵⁷ ibid.

⁵⁸ Constitution of Bangladesh, Article 18A.

generation and also suggests that certain resources are invested with a special nature.⁵⁹ Thus the trustees shall have a duty to make sure that the public trust properties are not being wasted.

3.2.2.2. Procedural duties

The duty of precaution: It is required of the state to take pre-cautionary measure to protect public trust property in all the development related functions. The Court in the Turag river has clarified that it is a legal obligation on the part of the state to abide by the obligations it took upon itself from Rio Declaration.⁶⁰ Principle 15 of the Declaration incorporates the duty of the state to take precautionary measures.

The duty to enforce polluter pays principle: In the Turag river, the court adopted the polluter pays principle in Bangladesh. The court made it clear that the hard-earned income of the people and their tax money cannot be used for restoring the Turag River back to its original form due to the encroachment and pollution of the river. While doing so, the Court relied on the authority of Principle 16 of the Rio Declaration which states that: “the polluter should in principle bear the cost of pollution with due regard to the public interest”.⁶¹ The court read Article 21 of the Constitution with Principle 16 of the Rio Declaration to observe that it is the obligation of the citizens to protect, preserve and not to cause destruction of the public trust property. Thus Ashraful Kamal J. declared that the court shall be the resort of the citizens if anyone destroys the public trust properties under its writ jurisdiction under Article 102(1) of the Constitution. It might be a moot question if actions in the writ jurisdiction can be brought against private persons. Following the *Datafin* test⁶² from the UK jurisdiction, the SCB has also adopted similar test utilizing the leeway in Article 102(1) of the Constitution. Since maintenance of the public trust property inevitably falls within the ‘affairs of the Republic’, suit can be brought against ‘any person’.⁶³ Thus if any person aggrieved brings a suit in the writ jurisdiction against any person who was caused injury to the public trust property, the Court shall be obliged to grant an order directing the polluter to pay such amount of damages as may be necessary to restore the public trust property.

⁵⁹ *T.N. Godavarman Thirumulpad v Union of India* AIR 2005 (SC) 4258.

⁶⁰ *Human Rights & Peace for Bangladesh* (n 39) 268.

⁶¹ *ibid*, 269.

⁶² *R (Datafin plc) v Panel on Take-overs and Mergers* (1987) 1 All ER 564.

⁶³ Such an approach was taken in *Moulana Md. Abdul Hakim v Bangladesh* (2014) 34 BLD 129. However, the development of this concept is yet in its early stage and there has no decision on this issue by the Appellate Division of the Supreme Court. But see Ridwanul Haque, ‘The “Datafin” Turn in Bangladesh: Opening Up Judicial Review of Private Bodies’ (*Adminlawblog*, 25 October 2017) <<https://adminlawblog.org/2017/10/25/ridwanul-hoque-the-datafin-turn-in-bangladesh-opening-up-judicial-review-of-private-bodies/>> accessed 21 April 2020.

The duty towards sustainable development: The needs of the future generation cannot be overlooked in the name of fulfilling the needs of the present generation. The Constitution of Bangladesh recognises the obligation of the state in ensuring the protection and improvement of the environment for the future generation.⁶⁴ Moreover, the Stockholm Declaration⁶⁵ and the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development⁶⁶ is also reflective of principle of striking a balance between environment and development. Thus, the environment, natural resources and bio-diversity cannot be destroyed for economic development of the country. The state must make a balance between the need for economic development and environmental pollution.⁶⁷ Such an approach is reflective of the sustainable development policy of the state.

The duty of furnishing information to beneficiaries (duty of accounting): Under the Private Trust Law, a trustee is bound to maintain clear and accurate accounts of the trust property.⁶⁸ However such an obligation upon the trustee is inherent in the trust law. In Bangladesh, there is no legislation to regulate the public trusts in general although there are laws to regulate the religious and charitable trusts.⁶⁹ Even in the absence of any specific law, the trustee of the public trust properties shall be responsible to make all the information about the accounts of the public trust property available in the online platform and update them regular in the online and offline site.

4. Critiques and responses to the critiques of public trust doctrine in Bangladesh

The legal literature in Bangladesh on the issue is seriously under-developed. The fact that there has been no literature on the critique of the DPT in Bangladesh is just one case-study of it. However, taking into consideration the U.S. academic scholarships, quite a few criticisms have been identified. In the following these identified criticisms shall be addressed in the context of Bangladesh.

4.1. Shaky origin

There has been huge criticism against the roman and common law roots of the DPT in the US legal academia. This criticism stems from Huffman's account that the Roman law and common law had nothing resembling to the concept of

⁶⁴ Constitution of Bangladesh, Article 18A.

⁶⁵ Stockholm Declaration on Human Environment 1972 U.N. Doc. A/CONF.48/4 at 2-65, Principles 1 and 2.

⁶⁶ Rio Declaration on Environment and Development 1992 UN Doc. A/CONF.151/26 (vol. I), 31 ILM 874 (1992), Principles 1, 4, 15, 16.

⁶⁷ *Human Rights & Peace for Bangladesh* (n 39) 260.

⁶⁸ Trust Act 1882, s 19.

⁶⁹ Charitable and Religious Trust Act 1920.

public trust and that Magna Carta had nothing to do with public rights.⁷⁰ In Bangladesh, the SCB have adopted the Saxion version of DPT by relying on the principle enunciated in *MC Mehta*.⁷¹ In doing so, the SCB has ignored a south-Asian root of the concept which has been even acknowledged in an International Court of Justice Decision.⁷² Therefore, even if one day the court decides to overturn its reliance of Saxion version of history, the Bangladeshi courts can still rely on the South Asian narrative of the development of the doctrine. Moreover, in Bangladesh the DPT has been developed as a constitutionally entrenched doctrine.⁷³ Ashraful Kamal J. observed that the DPT was incorporated into the original constitution of Bangladesh in Article 21 of the Constitution.⁷⁴ Later on, with the entrenchment of Article 18A and expansion of the meaning of Article 32 has only given it a solid grounding. Therefore, such a critique of shady historical background cannot stand in Bangladesh.

4.2. Inconsistent with rule of law

The DPT has also been alleged to be inconsistent with the concept of rule. The reason behind such an allegation is the contention that DPT allows the courts to “modify or abandon established common law principles in the name of present day notions of the public interest and public rights”.⁷⁵ Even if such an account is correct in those jurisdictions where DPT has developed as a common law based concept, such a contention does not hold true in Bangladesh because DPT has been a constitutionally entrenched provision since the its inception.

4.3. Judiciary led governance

The most prominent criticism against the DPT is that it has given too much power to the courts by incorporating a judiciary-based model of governance for the public trust properties.⁷⁶ Such a criticism stems from the traditional concept of separation of powers with the belief that only the legislature and executive possess the competency to deal with complex problems of environmental

⁷⁰ See for details, James L Huffman, ‘Speaking Inconvenient Truths: A History of Public Trust Doctrine’ (2007) 18 Duke Environmental Law and Policy Forum 1 (argues that the origin of DPT is not based on true facts to the extent of preserving public rights).

⁷¹ In all four cases involving DPT in Bangladesh, the Court has actively relied on the principle of *M C Mehta* (n 25).

⁷² See for details, *Hungary v Slovakia* (n 15).

⁷³ See for details, *Human Rights & Peace for Bangladesh v Bangladesh* (n 39).

⁷⁴ *Ibid.*

⁷⁵ See for details, James L Huffman, ‘Background Principles and the Rule of Law: Fifteen years after Lucas’ (2008) 35 Ecology Law Quarterly 1, 27.

⁷⁶ James L. Huffman, ‘Why Liberating the Public Trust Doctrine is bad for the Public’ (2015) 45(2) Environmental Law 337-377 (identified issues involving separation of powers, rule of law and due process).

concern.⁷⁷ However, it has to be kept in mind that the nature and environment has significantly deteriorated over the years although there has been consistent efforts of the legislature and executive government. This has happened due to the lobbying efforts of the big industries and the vulnerability of the government to such lobbying efforts. However, in Bangladesh the question about supremacy of any particular branch of the government does not arise because it is the Constitution that is supreme.⁷⁸ Therefore, all the branches of the government shall function according to the Constitution of Bangladesh. Moreover, since complete separation of powers is not feasible and non-existent even in the United States, following the global practice, Bangladesh has also adopted the doctrine of check and balance.⁷⁹ The doctrine of check and balance requires the judiciary to oversee the legality of the actions of legislature and the executive. In the name of water-tight compartmentalization, the judges cannot bypass their constitutional obligation towards public trust properties when there has been a manifest violation of citizen's right to enjoy public property. In this situation it is imperative that the members of the public are given the opportunity and legal standing to oversee the management of the public trust properties.

5. Future of public trust doctrine in Bangladesh

5.1. Importance of allowing the DPT to develop

The future of DPT in Bangladesh is really bright. It requires further academic discussion as to how the doctrine will gradually evolve and what areas it will touch. At the same time, it is important for us to let DPT develop itself. The reason is very obvious. The DPT is causing no harm to the rule of law, preservation of public trust properties although the potential development of the DPT can fill up the vacuum in the legislative framework which is very essential for the protection of various resources. Moreover, DPT plays at least two major roles in protecting the public properties. First, in the absence of any legislation, the DPT fills up the regulatory gap. Second, not only DPT fills up the legislative vacuum, it also sets the normative standard for the legislature in providing protection to the public trust property.

The prime reason why DPT should be let develop is that it fills the vacuum in the legal framework to give protection to the natural resources and ensures permanent sovereignty over natural resources. The multi-national corporations are constantly trying to siege the communal value of the natural

⁷⁷ Richard J. Lazarus, 'Changing Conceptions of Property and Sovereignty in Natural Resources: Questioning the Public Trust Doctrine' (1986) 71 *Iowa Law Review* 631, 633; Barton H Thompson Jr, 'Judicial Takings' (1990) 76 *Virginia Law Review* 1449.

⁷⁸ Constitution of Bangladesh, Article 7.

⁷⁹ *Bangladesh v Aftab Uddin* (2010) 30 BLD (AD) 1.

resources⁸⁰ and public properties. This is the same reason there is lack of positive law addressing the concerns of natural resources.⁸¹ At the same time there are other areas beyond natural resources where the judiciary needs tool to protect the public properties which shall be discussed in the following. Moreover, the DPT gives a normative standard and other tool to enact legislation on the area that are not being regulated by the positive law. Therefore, it is wise for the environment sensitive people to advocate for allowing the DPT to develop to address the unnoticed public properties.

5.2. Ways DPT can develop

5.2.1. Transformation of DPT into a cost-benefit analysis

Incorporation of Article 18A in the Constitution of Bangladesh makes a bold statement about the state's emphasis on the environmental protection and preservation. However, since it is assumable that the environmental consciousness will regularly be in violent clash with our developmental goal, the state shall move towards a balance of both interest transforming the entire DPT into a cost-benefit analysis. It requires to be mentioned that over the last century, the United States has also transformed into such a paradigm.⁸² In the sub-continent, the Indian Judiciary has engaged in, respecting separation of power theory, cost-benefit analysis between environmental concern and fundamental rights of the citizens.⁸³ Even in Bangladesh, the beginning of the journey to a cost-benefit analysis test can be noted. In *Human Rights and Peace for Bangladesh v Bangladesh*⁸⁴ ('*Thermal Power Plant*', hereinafter), the Court had to make a somewhat cost-benefit analysis between the need of the energy supply and preservation of marine life. The court finally directed the government to look for sites that will cause lesser or minimal harm. In *Advocate Asaduzzaman Siddiqui and others v Bangladesh*⁸⁵, the court acknowledged that since no nation can deny economic development and economic development itself is an antithesis of natural balance, all the developed nations are found to strike balance between economic development and its cost upon environment. Keeping the damage at the minimal Level has always been the policy everywhere. Thus, in future the

⁸⁰ See for details, Hope M Babcock, 'The Public Trust Doctrine: What a Tall Tale they Tell' (2009) 61 South Carolina Law Review 393.

⁸¹ Mary Christina Wood, 'Advancing the Sovereign Trust of Government to Safeguard the Environment for Present and Future Generations (Part II): Instilling a Fiduciary Obligation in Governance' (2009) 39 Environmental Law 91, 103.

⁸² For details on the US approach to the situation see, Matthew Thor Kirsch, 'Upholding the Public Trust in State Constitutions' (1997) 46 Duke Law Journal 1169.

⁸³ *Narmada Bachao Andolan v Union of India* (2000) 10 SCC 664; *Rural Litigation and Entitlement Kendra, Dehradun and Others v State of U.P. and Others* AIR 1985 SC 652; *Karnataka Industrial Areas Development Board v Sri C. Kenchappa and Others* AIR 2006 SC 2038.

⁸⁴ *Human Rights and Peace for Bangladesh v Bangladesh* (2012) Writ Petition No. 8282/2010.

⁸⁵ *Advocate Asaduzzaman Siddiqui and others v Bangladesh* (2013) WP No.10937/2013, para 5.

DPT will impose ban on state actions unless that passes the cost-benefit test. However, taking into consideration the current developments so far, the following threefold test can be theorized:

1. Has the government taken necessary measures to minimize the negative impact on the public trust property to the maximum level?
2. Is there any other alternative place where the project can be shifted for better preservation of the public trust property?
3. Whether the socio-economic impact of the project would supersede the negative impacts on the public trust property?

5.2.2. Expansion of the public trust to new resources

The Constitution of Bangladesh in its Part II embodies the Fundamental Principles of State Principles. The constitutional status of this part of the constitution is as follows:

8(2). The principles set out in this Part shall be fundamental to the governance of Bangladesh, shall be applied by the State in the making of laws, shall be a guide to the interpretation of the Constitution and of the other laws of Bangladesh, and shall form the basis of the work of the State and of its citizens, but shall not be judicially enforceable.

Unlike the Indian Constitution⁸⁶, the Bangladesh Constitution does make it imperative for the judiciary to use part II provisions as a “guide to interpretation of the Constitution”. The academic commentators are also of the same view that using the leeway in “guide to interpretation”, the courts can at least develop contents in enforcing a constitutional obligation on the part of the state.⁸⁷ With time the courts will try to widen the ambit of the DPT in Bangladesh. Thus it will try to incorporate the contents from the explicit environmental protection article

⁸⁶ Similar provision of the Indian Constitution can be found in Article 37 where it states: “The provisions contained in this Part shall not be enforceable by any court, but the principles therein laid down are nevertheless fundamental in the governance of the country and it shall be the duty of the State to apply these principles in making laws.” While interpreting the Bangladesh Constitution, I argue that looking at the relevant provision through the lens of Comparative Constitutional Law of India is important since the Constituent Assembly of Bangladesh explicitly debated on the model of Indian Constitution.

⁸⁷ See for details, M Waheduzzaman, ‘Judicial Enforcement of Socio-Economic Rights in Bangladesh: Theoretical aspects from comparative perspective’ in Mizanur Rahman (ed), *Human Rights and Environment* (Dhaka: ELCOP, 2011) 57-80; M Waheduzzaman, ‘Economic, Social and Cultural Rights under the Constitution: Critical Evaluation of Judicial Jurisprudence in Bangladesh’ (2014) 14(1 & 2) *Bangladesh Journal of Law*; M Waheduzzaman, ‘Inclusion and Enforcement of ESC Rights under State Constitutions: An Appraisal’ (2015) 3 *Jahangirnagar University Journal of Law*; M Jashim Ali Chowdhury, ‘Does inconsistency with Fundamental Principles of State Policy invalidate a Law?’ (2009) 5 *BRAC University Journal* 71-75; Md. Reajul Hasan Shohag and ABM Asrafuzzaman, ‘Enforcing Socio-Economic Rights Judicially: Experiments in Bangladesh, India and South Africa’ (2012) 3 *Northern Uni. Journal of Law* 87.

of the Bangladesh Constitution and extend the protection to “bio-diversity, wetlands, forests and wild life for the present and future citizens”.⁸⁸ Moreover, the DPT can also expand its purview to provide protection to national cultural traditions, heritage of people of Bangladesh, local culture and tradition of tribes, minor races, ethnic sects and communities.⁸⁹ If we look into the whole discussion from a bird’s eye view, it is clear that the DPT can turn to be epitome of negative enforcement of entire part II of the constitution. That means if the state actions are manifestly contrary to the objectives of the Part II provisions of the Constitution, the Court shall impose ban on those state actions.

5.2.3. Developing privacy regulation

The Constitution of Bangladesh guarantees to right to privacy of the correspondence and other means of communication of the citizens.⁹⁰ However, such a constitutional provision is inadequate to give protection to the citizens from data leakage out of big data industries. Back in 2016, when the Government of Bangladesh initiated a mandatory biometric sim registration, questions were raised as to the legality of the system since it places tremendous trust on the Telecommunication corporations. Thus when a writ petition was filed, the court issued a rule as to the legality of the biometric registration.⁹¹ The government took the position that the mobile phone operators were merely cross checking the finger prints with the database of the National ID card.⁹² After a hearing on the rule, the Court legalised the biometric sim registration. However, such a legalisation brings into forefront the issue of government responsibility in protecting the most delicate data of the individuals of the country. The legal regime is totally silent in placing obligation on the part of the government. This loophole creates a possibility that such a vacuum shall be addressed by judicial innovation, i.e. considering the national database a public trust property. The government shall be under the obligation to take all sorts of measure to protect the database.

6. Conclusion

Although the DPT has been a part of Bangladeshi law since the beginning of the constitutional framework of Bangladesh, it took time for the judiciary to acknowledge it and use it as a tool to provide protection to the public properties.

⁸⁸ Constitution of Bangladesh, Article 18A.

⁸⁹ *ibid*, Article 23.

⁹⁰ *ibid*, Article 43.

⁹¹ Ashutosh Sarkar and Muhammad Zahidul Islam, ‘HC questions legality: Issues rule on authorities amid public fear of misuse of their personal data’ *The Daily Star* (Dhaka, 15 March 2016) <<https://www.thedailystar.net/frontpage/hc...legality-791446>> accessed 26 April 2020.

⁹² UNB, ‘No fingerprint stored during SIM re-registration: Tarana’ *The Independent* (Dhaka, 12 June 2016) <<http://www.theindependentbd.com/post/47244>> accessed 27 April 2020.

Unlike many jurisdictions, the DPT has a constitutional root in Bangladesh and has an autochthonous South Asian origin. Therefore, the popular criticisms against the doctrine does not hold value at all. Moreover, in this article, the proper meaning of the DPT and the scope of such doctrine has been elaborated taking into consideration all the judicial decision by the SCB so far. It shows that the DPT can be utilized in areas far beyond its current usage for protecting natural resources and environmental elements.

This article theorized a threefold test for the judiciary to use it as a tool to adjudicate matters related to natural resources or public properties at large. It is expected that the judiciary will take the threefold test in judicial approval of projects involving harm to the public trust properties. The government also needs to run the threefold test before initiating any project involving public trust properties. The legislature should consider the test to ensure none of their Acts are violative of the constitutional mandate to protect public trust properties. This Article also predicts that the judiciary shall extend the ambit of the DPT in Bangladesh in view of the Part II provisions of the Constitution and in developing protection for privacy issues in the absence of any legislative framework. With concerted efforts from all three branches of the state machinery, the public trust properties can be properly protected and preserved.

